

MENTAL DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN**Matrizayeva Bonu Saburjon qizi**

Urgench State University, Pedagogy Faculty, Department of Preschool Education, student

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Abstract. *This article highlights the issues of mental development of preschool children, the functions of mental upbringing, the methods of mental improvement of preschool children based on the collaboration of preschool educational organizations.*

Keywords: *preschool educational organizations, educator, family, mental upbringing, children*

ПСИХИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

Аннотация. *В данной статье освещаются вопросы психического развития детей дошкольного возраста, функции психического воспитания, методы психического совершенствования детей дошкольного возраста на основе сотрудничества дошкольных образовательных организаций.*

Ключевые слова: *дошкольные образовательные организации, воспитатель, семья, психическое воспитание, дети.*

INTRODUCTION

The development of preschool children is a gradual process, and mental development is also improved step-by-step.

Intelligence is a set of cognitive processes, starting from sensation and perception, and includes the processes of thinking and life. Mental activity requires that attention is always focused on a certain goal. A person's intelligence is determined by the characteristics of his success in his main activity. Therefore, the future success of children depends on their mental development.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mental development can be understood as the process of development of mental power and thinking resulting from all quantitative possibilities of life effects and consequences.

Our people call wise people who have mature mental education, sharp mind, wit and intelligence. Wisdom is mental consciousness. Wisdom is the greatest and noblest virtue of man. Wisdom is such a rare gift that not everyone is blessed with. That is probably why it is said in folk wisdom, "The crown of the mind is made of gold, not everyone has gold." Since the beginning of mankind, all the scientists and virtuous people, poets and writers who have grown up among people have risen to the level of notable people of their time by acquiring perfect knowledge. Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Mahmud Koshgari, Alisher Navoi, Abdullah Avloni and others, western scientists, such as Jan Amos Komensky, K. D. Ushinsky, J. J. Rousseau and others made great discoveries in all fields of science by acquiring perfect knowledge [2].

By intelligence, Ibn Sina understands the innate talent of a person, the ability to think that is formed in the process of knowing. The intelligence is divided into two categories:

1. Theoretical intelligence is the perception of the general things in existence.
2. Practical intelligence is one of the abilities that can be seen as a motivation in choosing things.

Abdulla Avloni, who is considered one of the great enlighteners of his time, also calls on young people to be knowledgeable. He glorifies reason and knowledge and says, "Intelligence is the perfect and only god of man. The soul is the worker, the intelligence is the initiator," he writes.

At the age of preschool education, knowledge is consistently enriched at a rapid pace, children's speech is formed, cognitive processes are further improved, the child acquires the simplest methods of mental activity. Ensuring mental development of children of preschool age is of great importance for all their future activities. The child develops mentally under the influence of the social environment. In the process of dealing with the people around him, he learns the language and the system of concepts formed with it. As a result, at preschool age, along with intellectual development, the child acquires the language so much that he can freely use it as a means of communication.

RESULTS

The task of mental education is determined by its content, method and organization. Pedagogical-psychological science, in order to effectively solve the tasks of mental education, firstly, to correctly use the child's capabilities, and secondly, to find ways to avoid excessive stress, which can cause general fatigue of the child's organism. Preschool education is engaged in studying the laws and possibilities of mental development of children.

Mental education is of great importance in preparing a child for school education. The acquisition of knowledge by the child, the development of mental activity, the acquisition of mental skills and abilities, serves as a source of preparation for the future labor activity, for their successful study at school.

The tasks of mental education include:

- acquisition of scientific knowledge of the specified volume;
- forming a worldview;
- development of mental strength, talents and abilities;
- development of interest in knowledge;
- development of personal potential;
- formation of cognitive activity;
- development of the needs to constantly supplement one's knowledge, increase the level of general educational preparation;
- equipping learners with methods of cognitive activity;
- thinking ability, formation of creative activity experiences.

DISCUSSION

The formation of mathematical ideas is one of the most important processes in the mental development of preschool children. Mathematics takes a leading place in mental development. Not only games that shape the mathematical imagination, but also music are of great help for the mental development of children in the cooperation of the preschool educational organization and the family. Music is an art form that occupies a large place in our cultural life and is of great importance in the development of human personality. Music education is one of the main and complex aspects of the education of sophistication, it teaches to correctly perceive and appreciate the beautiful things around. Music influenced mental development, accelerated the growth of cells responsible for human intelligence. In the school of Pythagoras, mathematics lessons were conducted together with the music. This process increased the efficiency and mental activity of the brain. Therefore, the use of mathematics and music in the family is considered to be the most effective method for the mental development of children. In addition, it is necessary to familiarize the child with the surroundings. In this, children will have the opportunity to acquire knowledge by listening, seeing and feeling.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, in the process of educating preschool children, it is necessary to pay attention to their mental development. This process is the main task not only of the educator, but also of the parents. Mental development affects a child's learning. It is advisable for parents to pay attention to their child's development and, in consultation with the educator, to use various games and tasks for his mental development in the family circle or in everyday life. A good result can be achieved if children's mental development is taken into account and methods based on this interest are used.

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